

BMF CP113: Environmental and Health Value Consideration and Home Smart Energy Management System Adoption Willingness across Urban and Rural United States

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“[...] the age of technology has arrived, and Kingfisher has decided it’s time for something new: Technological Innovation. Innovation can help Kingfisher conserve energy while maintaining a sense of tranquility, which is suitable for an increasingly advanced age with diminishing physical strength.”

—In “Innovation,” [Wild Wise Weird](#) (2024)

1. Project description

1.1. Main objectives

The current study is conducted to examine the following research questions:

- How is the consideration of environmental and health values in appliance, technology, and home modification decision-making associated with the willingness to adopt a

smart home energy management system?

- Is the relationship between the consideration of environmental and health values in appliance, technology, and home modification decision-making, and willingness to adopt a smart home energy management system, conditional on the estimates of long-term benefits?
- Is the relationship between the consideration of environmental and health values in appliance, technology, and home modification decision-making, and willingness to adopt a smart home energy management system, conditional on the upfront financial support?
- What are the differences in these relationships between families residing in urban and rural areas?

Findings from this study are expected to contribute to promoting the eco-surplus culture and sustainable development [1].

1.2. Materials

The Granular Interaction Thinking Theory (GIT) will be employed for the conceptual development of this study, while the Bayesian Mindsponge Framework (BMF) analytics will be utilized for statistical analysis [2,3]. The dataset comprises responses from 9919 U.S. residents of single-family and small multifamily homes [4]. Statistical analyses will be conducted using the `bayesvl` R package, which utilizes the Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) algorithm for estimation [5].

For the sake of research transparency and reducing research and reproducibility costs, we have stored all data and computer code on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/16407815>.

1.3. Main findings

The preliminary analysis indicates that among rural households, consideration of environmental values in decision-making is positively associated with willingness to adopt. Upfront financial support can amplify the positive effect, while the estimate of long-term benefits has an ambiguous moderating effect (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: The estimated posterior distributions.

2. Collaboration procedure

Portal users should follow these steps to register to participate in this research project:

1. Create an account on the website (preferably using an institutional email).
2. Comment your name, affiliation, and your desired role in the project below this post.
3. Patiently wait for the formal agreement on the project from the AISDL mentor.

If you have further inquiries, please contact us at aisdl_team@mindsponge.info

If you have been invited to join the project by an AISDL member, you are still encouraged to follow the above formal steps.

All the resources for conducting and writing the research manuscript will be distributed upon project participation.

AISDL mentor for this project: **Minh-Hoang Nguyen.**

AISDL members who have joined this project: **Quan-Hoang Vuong, Viet-Phuong La.**

The research project strictly adheres to scientific integrity standards, including authorship rights and obligations, without incurring an economic burden at participants' expenses.

References

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[3] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH, La VP. (2022). *The mindsponge and BMF analytics for innovative thinking in social sciences and humanities*. Walter de Gruyter GmbH. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/8367405102/>

[4] Fuentes TL, et al. (2025). A dataset for understanding self-reported patterns influencing residential energy decisions. *Scientific Data*, **12**, 1273. <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41597-025-05335-8>

[5] Vuong QH, La VP. (2025). Package 'bayesvl' version 1.0.0. <https://books.google.com/books/about?id=znleEQAAQBAJ>

[6] Vuong QH. (2024). *Wild Wise Weird*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/BOBG2NNHY6>

